

Pest survey in Kalutara district, Sri Lanka

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We surveyed rice insect pests and natural enemies in farmers' fields in the 1984 Apr-Aug growing season.

Kalutara district was divided into 3 districts and 2 fields of 0.6 ha or more were selected in each district. Distance between fields was at least 5 km. The rice variety grown in the selected fields was the most common variety.

Assessments were made once a month from seedling to ripening. Fifteen sweeps/field were taken for insect counts and five 1-m² samples were observed for damage.

The harmful insects present in considerable amounts were whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) at the vegetative phase and paddy bug *Leptocorisa oratorius* at the reproductive phase.

Natural enemies found included spiders, dragonflies, mirid bugs, and hymenopteran parasites (see table).

The WBPH at the vegetative phase dropped in number with crop age. This decrease may be due to the presence of natural enemies.

Farmers had used chemical control in previous seasons. □

Number of insects/15 sweeps in farmers' fields. Sri Lanka, 1984.

District	Area	Insect pests (no.)		Natural enemies (no.)			
		WBPH	Paddy bug	Spiders	Dragonflies	Mirid bugs	Hymenopterans
<i>Seedling stage</i>							
Kalutara	Nagoda	0	0	0	3	16	0
	Uggalboda	51	0	0	3	1	0
Horana	Kananwila	23	0	0	0	5	18
	Kulupana	9	0	0	1	5	86
Matugama	Matugama	16	0	1	7	5	5
	Bellana	56	0	0	0	2	13
<i>Tillering</i>							
Kalutara	Nagoda	18	8	1	2	3	0
	Uggalboda	133	9	6	14	9	0
Horana	Kananwila	17	2	10	1	0	13
	Kulupana	29	136	0	1	0	—
Matugama	Matugama	35	0	2	4	0	12
	Bellana	0	0	1	3	40	40
<i>Booting</i>							
Kalutara	Nagoda	0	18	22	2	1	13
	Uggalboda	0	36	4	1	14	22
Horana	Kananwila	19	8	3	0	1	24
	Kalupana	2	16	2	1	2	13
Matugama	Matugama	30	12	2	1	0	0
	Bellana	2	0	1	6	0	0
<i>Flowering</i>							
Kalutara	Nagoda	0	52	12	4	0	5
	Uggalboda	0	12	1	0	0	0
Horana	Kananwila	0	19	9	0	0	0
	Kulupana	0	48	2	0	0	0
Matugama	Matugama	0	67	0	0	2	10
	Bellana	0	35	0	1	0	0
<i>Ripening</i>							
Kalutara	Nagoda	0	25	0	5	0	0
	Uggalboda	0	144	0	0	0	0
Horana	Kananwila	0	87	0	0	0	0
	Kalupana	0	170	0	0	0	0
Matugama	Matugama	0	11	1	—	—	—
	Bellana	—	—	—	—	—	—

Trap crop for green leafhopper (GLH) and tungro (RTV) management

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A trap crop is a small, early planting of a crop that is more attractive to insect pests than the crop to be protected and effective enough to justify using it instead of other control measures.

We tested using a trap crop instead of intensive chemical control of *Nephotettix virescens* in May-Sep 1986. RTV-susceptible IR42 was used as both trap crop and main crop.

Table 1. RTV incidence in ricefields with and without a trap crop.^a IRRI, May-Sep 1986.

Treatment ^b	Date planted	Proportionate area/ha	RTV incidence ^c (%)	Combined RTV incidence (%)
2-row trap crop	9 May	0.074	0.3	8.5 a
Main crop	23 May	0.926	8.2 a	
3-row trap crop	9 May	0.109	0.5	7.5 a
Main crop	23 May	0.891	7.0 a	
4-row trap crop	9 May	0.144	0.5	5.2 a
Main crop	23 May	0.856	4.7 a	
Treated control ^d	9 May	1.000	6.4 a	6.4 a
Untreated control ^e	23 May	1.000	36.8 b	

^aAv of 4 replications. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bTrap crops were sprayed. ^cProportionate RTV incidence (%) in trap crop was not analyzed. ^dMain crop fields sprayed with cypermethrin @ 0.05 kg ai/ha. ^eUnsprayed fields.

In trap-crop fields, 2, 3, or 4 border rows were planted 15 d before the main crop and sprayed each week up to 60 d

after transplanting (DT) with cypermethrin at 0.05 kg ai/ha. The main crop was not sprayed.

Fields without a trap crop, but sprayed with cypermethrin, were the treated control. Unsprayed fields without a trap crop were the untreated control.

Plot size was 11 × 17 m. Each treatment was replicated four times.

At 65 DT, RTV incidence was significantly higher in the untreated control than in trap or insecticide-treated fields (Table 1). Relatively higher nymphal and adult GLH populations were recorded.

Yields were significantly higher in trap and insecticide-treated fields than in the untreated control (Table 2). Although yield was highest in insecticide-treated fields, the cost of cypermethrin lowered net gain. Limited insecticide use also conserves natural enemies of rice pests. □

Table 2. Value of yields with and without trap crop after deducting cost of cypermethrin^a. IRRI, May–Sep 1986.

Treatment	Area (ha)		Combined yield (t/ha)	Value of yield ^b (\$/ha)	Cypermethrin applied ^c (liters/ha)	Cost ^d (\$/ha)	Net value (\$/ha)
	Trap crop	Main crop					
2-row trap crop and main crop	0.074	0.926	4.5 a	787.50	0.592	14.21	713.29 a
3-row trap crop and main crop	0.109	0.891	4.2 a	735.00	0.872	20.93	714.07 a
4-row trap crop and main crop	0.144	0.856	4.4 a	770.00	1.152	27.65	742.35 a
Treated control	0	1.000	4.9 a	857.50	8.000	192.00	665.50 ab
Untreated control	0	1.000	3.3 b	577.50	0	0	577.50 b

^a Av of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^b US\$ = P20; value of rice (NFA price) = \$0.175/kg. ^c Eight applications to trap crop rows and treated control plots @ 0.05 kg ai/ha per treatment. ^d Cost of cypermethrin Jul 1986 = \$24/liter.

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Rice thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) effect on yield

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We evaluated thrips damage and subsequent yield in highly susceptible variety Bg 94-1. We assumed that natural thrips infestation would be uniform over all plots, if not controlled. Carbofuran at 1 kg ai/ha was used in an

experiment in late Nov 1983. A second experiment used different insecticides. Damage was rated according to the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 3–4 wk after sowing. After assessment, the plants were fully protected from other pest attacks.

In carbofuran-treated plots, thrips damage was rated as 1; in untreated

control plots, 7–9. Average grain yield in treated plots (3.34 t/ha) was significantly different from that in the untreated plots (2.34 t/ha) at 5% level of probability. Plots treated with different chemicals had a control rating of 1 for all but triazophos, which rated 5; untreated plots rated 7 (see figure). Yields varied. □

Thrips damage and rice yield under chemical control, Sri Lanka, 1983.

Influence of age of crop and time of planting on gall midge (GM) incidence

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Rice GM *Orseolia oryzivora* is a serious

pest of wet season (WS) rice at Edozhigi, an irrigated area in Nigeria. The rainy season in this area is Jun-Oct and farmers transplant in Sep.

We measured GM incidence on FARO 27 and FARO 29 in the 1985 WS on samples of 50 hills/variety, replicated 3 times. Percentage of silvershoots was calculated as the ratio

GM incidence by age of rice crop. Edozhigi, Nigeria, 1985 wet season.

Days after transplanting	Silvershoots ^a (%)		
	FARO 27	FARO 29	Mean
30	13.8 (21.6)	11.8 (17.4)	12.8
40	15.4 (22.6)	18.0 (25.1)	16.7
50	14.5 (21.7)	18.2 (25.2)	16.4
60	7.9 (16.1)	15.3 (22.9)	11.6
70	7.7 (16.0)	10.4 (18.6)	9.1
LSD (0.05)	10.2	6.7	

^a Figures in parentheses are transformed angular values, LSDs refer to them.